

THE ERA OF FLEXIBLE STUDY AND WORK IN HIGHER EDUCATION HAS BEGUN

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Abstract

On June 4, 2023 the Malaysian Higher Education Ministry (MOHE) announced that they will introduce a hybrid and flexible teaching and learning system at universities in the country. This long-awaited announcement is the starting point towards the implementation of flexible educational process in the country. This announcement has been welcomed by many especially by the varsities students as many of the students see this new mode of teaching and learning process as the suitable way to pursue their higher academic scroll in line with the current changes which occurred around the world due the Covid-19 pandemic which started in early 2020. With the Covid-19 pandemic radically reshaping the education system, universities may never be the same again. Covid-19 pandemic has forced many universities in Malaysia and other countries to rapidly shift toward online mode. Though Covid-19 pandemic seem coming to the end by the time this research in prepared, the idea of flexibility and online study seem has attracted many students. The idea of flexibility not only has attracted students, it has also attracted the educators and the administrators in the universities. Universities educators and administrators want the working style in the university to be change toward hybrid and flexibility as well. The existence of many new communication technologies allow teaching and learning process including working related activities to be carry out through online. By offering flexibility, both students and workers can save their time, energy and money more. There are many advantages which flexibility can offers to both university students and the workers. However, we should also remember, to implement flexibility and offer online teaching and learning process effectively, it would require us to have all the necessary equipment's in place. The internet line should also be effective enough for us to carry out all the teaching and learning process and working related activities smoothly. Having said so, we must never abandon the idea of flexibility in the country educational and working sectors. Need to be remember, the Malaysian government has taken many steps in recent years to allow the idea of flexibility to use within the country educational sector and working sector. Recently, the Malaysian government has taken a huge step amending the country main labour law statute namely the Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] to allow flexible working arrangement (FWA) in the country. Thus, the main objective of this research is to further analyse the idea of flexibility and its implementation particularly in the higher educational institutions. The research will look into the benefits it would bring to our educational system particularly towards the country higher institutions. In order to make flexibility effective, the Malaysian government need to include this issue under the country national educational policy. Once included, long term commitment can be given to make flexibility as part of the country national educational system regardless the change in the government administration and the country political landscape.

Keywords: Flexibility, education, work

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Without doubt, Covid-19 pandemic which has struck the world in early 2020 has changed our life forever. Some of the impact of Covid-19 will remain with us forever. Among it is the dependence and utilization of technology to ease our daily life. Those who are working in the office eager to have flexibility in their work and those who are still study either in school or university now wish to have remote learning. The world as we knew before the start of the Covid-19 pandemic has ended. Though there are some people who wanted the world to be run exactly as it were before the start of Covid-19 pandemic, not all things will be the same again. As a human being, we need to evolve with the change of time. All of us need to move forward not backward. Using technology has become part and parcel of our life. We cannot totally exclude our dependence and use of technology in our daily activities whether we like it or not. Instead of seeing technology as an enemy, we should open up our mind and embrace it for our benefits. Almost all countries started to make changes either through their social habit, country administration and legislations to meet the current changes due to the spread of Covid-19. In Malaysia for example, changes have come through its legislation. The country main labour legislation namely the Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] has been subjected to amendments to adapt the current reality of working environment due to Covid-19 pandemic. The amendments were presented in March 2022. (Malaysiakini, March 23, 2022). The amendment was supposed to be enforced on September 1, 2022 (Malay Mail, June 23, 2022). However, due to some plea from the employers, the enforcement of the amendments was carried out on January 1, 2023 (Free Malaysia Today, August 26, 2022). The largest change to the employment landscape in Malaysia pursuant to the Employment (Amendment of First Schedule) Order 2022 is that the First Schedule has been widened to include any person who has entered into a contract of service, meaning the Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] now applies to all employees irrespective of wage. Notwithstanding this, certain provisions in respect of overtime payments and termination benefits will not apply to employees earning more than RM4000/month. The previous position was that only employees earning up to RM2000/month were protected under the Employment Act 1955 [Act 265]. This widening of the Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] scope means employers should ensure that their employment contracts comply with the minimum standards set under the Employment Act 1955 [Act 265]. Any employment terms that are less favourable to the employee can be rendered void and unenforceable. The 60 days of maternity leave entitlement under the Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] has been increased to 98 days. This is a welcome change to match international labour standards and ensure that working mothers have sufficient time to recuperate and care for their child. The Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] now provides working fathers 7 days of paid paternity leave for each confinement, up to a limit of 5 confinements. Although 7 days may not be enough, it is a good start in the Malaysian framework. The Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] now provides that employees can submit a written application for flexible working arrangement (FWA) to modify their hours, days or place of work. Any application must be approved or rejected by the employer within 60 days in writing, and any rejection must be justified. Employers must also now exhibit conspicuously at the place of employment, a notice to raise awareness on sexual harassment. The Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] now provides that the maximum working hours for employees are reduced from 48 to 45 hours per week. This means that employees are now entitled to overtime payments for any extra hours spent beyond the 45 hours. Prior to the amendment, an employee is entitled to paid sick leave of 14 to 21 days, depending on their length of employment, where no hospitalisation is required. Where hospitalisation is required, an employee is entitled to 60 days of paid sick leave provided that the total number of paid sick leaves taken in a year does not exceed 60 days. Pursuant to the new amendment, the 60 days of paid sick leave for hospitalisations are now in addition to the 14 to 21 days of paid sick leave where hospitalisation is not necessary. New provisions have been included to prohibit forced labour whereby employers who threaten, deceive or force an employee to do any work or prevent that employee from leaving a place of work after work is done, are liable to a fine not exceeding RM100,000 or imprisonment not exceeding 2 years or both. Employers must obtain prior approval from the Director General of Labour before employing foreign employees. The Director General can approve such applications and fix conditions to them where necessary. On the other hand, if a foreign employee is terminated, the employer must inform the Director General of Labour within 30 days. If the foreign employee absconds from the employment, the employer shall inform the Director General within 14 days. The Director General of Labour has power to inquire and determine any disputes and matters relating to discrimination in employment. The DG can make an order and any employer failing to comply with said order commits an offence. On the whole, employers are advised to review their employment terms and policies to ensure compliance with the Employment Act 1955 [Act 265] to avoid sanction. (Can read further

Dextor Tilo, January 4, 2023). Interesting for us to note that among the changes which been mentioned in this particular amendment is the insertion of flexible working arrangement for the employees in the country. This is a very significant development for Malaysia as this is the first time, the idea of flexibility has gained to its foot through legislation. It is the researcher humble believe, from this legal recognition, the idea of flexibility will start to flourish in coming years in the country.

Since everybody started to talk about flexibility, the education sectors in the country also wanted to make changes of their own. On June 4, 2023, the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education Ministry (MOHE) said that it will introduce a hybrid and flexible learning system at universities. Its minister, Datuk Seri Mohamed Khaled Nordin said under this system, tertiary students will attend lectures at the university for the first and final year of their studies only. According to him "In the middle years, students will be given a choice and the flexibility to study from home, without having to attend physical classes". He said through this initiative students can organise their activities more flexibly and they will be able to save their tertiary education costs. Through this initiative, it will give some advantages such as, can reduce the amount of loans and education costs, opening up space for students work or do things that require them to not be on campus. At the same time, it opens up opportunities for graduates enter the job market a year earlier. The Minister also said that a total of 95 bachelor's degree programs from 19 public universities in the country were ready to implement a flexible learning system starting with admission for the year 2023/2024 academic session. On the same note, he said that the duration of study for some programmes would be shortened from four to three years (Shathana Kasinathan, June 4, 2023). The idea of hybrid and flexible learning started to arise after the country was struck by Covid-19 in early 2020. The medical response and preparedness to the Covid-19 outbreak in Malaysia was overseen by the former Director-General of Health Tan Sri Dato' Seri Dr. Haji Noor Hisham Abdullah under the Malaysian Ministry of Health (MOH) of three successive governments led by Tun Dr. Mahathir Mohamad (2018 – 2020), Tan Sri Muhyiddin Yassin (2020 – 2021) and Dato' Sri Ismail Sabri Yaakob (2021 – 2022). The first Covid-19 cases in Malaysia were confirmed among travellers from China in Johor via Singapore on 25 January 2020 (Sipalan, Joseph; Holmes, Sam, January 25, 2020) and continued to be limited to a few imported cases until March 2020, when several local clusters emerged. The most notable was a Tablighi Jamaat religious gathering in Sri Petaling, Kuala Lumpur that sparked a massive spike in local cases and imported cases to neighboring countries. (Ng, Kate, March 16, 2020). By the end of March 2020, the total number of cases had risen from below 30 to over 2,000 active cases across every state and federal territory in the country. As of December 15, 2022, with over 4.8 million confirmed Covid-19 cases and over 36,000 deaths, the country was ranked third in the number of Covid-19 cases in Southeast Asia behind Vietnam and Indonesia, and fourth in the number of Covid-19 deaths in Southeast Asia behind Indonesia, the Philippines, and Vietnam. (Please refer to the Southeast Asia Covid-19 Tracker, 2022 and the Malaysian Ministry of Health (MOH) official website for data and insights on COVID-19 2022).

In response to the surge of cases in March 2020, the Malaysian government led by the then Prime Minister Tan Sri Muhyiddin Yassin imposed a nationwide lockdown known as the Movement Control Order (MCO), which came into effect on 18 March 2020. (The Prime Minister's Special Message on COVID-19, March 16, 2020). On 16 March 2020, Prime Minister Tan Sri Muhyiddin Yassin made an official speech and officially promulgated the movement control order under the Prevention and Control of Infectious Diseases Act 1988 [Act 342] and the Police Act 1967 [Act 344]. (Junhairi Alyasa, March 16, 2020). The order included the following restrictions: General prohibition of mass movements and gatherings across the country including religious, sports, social and cultural activities. To enforce this prohibition, all houses of worship and business premises would be closed, except for supermarkets, public markets, grocery stores and convenience stores selling everyday necessities. Specifically, for Muslims, the adjournment of all religious activities in mosques including Friday prayers would be in line with the decision made on 15 March 2020 by the Special Muzakarah Meeting of the National Council for Islamic Affairs; Sanctions covering all Malaysians travelling abroad. For those who have just returned from overseas, they would be required to undergo a health check and a 14-day quarantine (or self-quarantine); Restrictions on the entry of all tourists and foreign visitors into the country; Closure of all kindergartens, government and private schools including daily schools, boarding schools, international schools, tahfiz centres and another primary, secondary and pre-university institutions; Closure of all public and private higher education institutions (IPTs) and skills training institutes nationwide; and Closure of all government and private premises except those involved in essential services (water, electricity, energy, telecommunications, postal, transportation, irrigation, oil, gas, fuel, lubricants, broadcasting, finance, banking, health, pharmacy, fire, prison, port, airport, safety, defence, cleaning, retail and food supply). The MCO, which was originally to be ended on 31 March 2020, was extended to early May 2020. By early May, the MCO had led to a gradual decline in daily infections. The government progressively relaxed lockdown restrictions in a staggered phase; beginning with the Conditional Movement Control Order (CMCO) on 4 May 2020, which allows most business sectors to be reopened under strict standard operating

procedures (SOPs), followed by the Recovery Movement Control Order (RMCO) on 10 June 2020. The government had planned to end the RMCO on 31 August 2020 but due to the continuous detection of imported cases, measures were extended until the end of the year, with several sectors remaining closed and strict travel restrictions from several countries remaining in place. The strict orders which was carried out through the first MCO in the country has force many workplaces in the country to closed and workers been allowed to work their home. Starting from this period many employees in the country both in public and private sectors started to force themselves to learn to use and utilized any available technologies to perform their duties and responsibilities remotely from their houses. It is strongly believed, the first implementation of strict MCO in the country in March 2020 has given rise to the idea of work from home (WFH) policy as well as flexible working arrangement (FWA). The implementation of the strict MCO also was believe one of the strong factors which give rise to remote or flexible learning process in the country educational sector.

Covid-19 pandemic resulted in the closure of the vast majority of schools and universities worldwide including in Malaysia for in-person learning. (Unesco, March 4, 2020). Many schools and universities moved to online remote learning through platforms including but not limited to Zoom, Cisco Webex, Google Classroom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, D2L, Edgenuity and many more (Jonathan Raymond, April 28, 2020). Concerns arose over the impact of this transition on students without access to an internet-enabled device or a stable internet connection. Distanced or remote education during the Covid-19 pandemic has interrupted synchronous learning for many students and teachers; where educators were no longer able to teach in real-time and could only switch to asynchronous instruction, this significantly and negatively affected their coping with the transition, and posed various legal issues, especially in terms of copyright. (Deflem, Mathieu, 2021). A recent study about the benefits and drawbacks of online learning found that students have had a harder time producing their own work. The study suggests educators should cut back on the amount of information taught and incorporate more activities during the lesson, in order for students to create their own work (Mukhtar, Khadijah; Javed, Kainat; Arooj, Mahwish; Sethi, Ahsan, May 2020). Though schools and universities are slow to adapt to new technologies, Covid-19 required schools and universities to adapt and learn how to use new digital and online learning tools. Web conferencing has become more popular since 2007. Researchers have found that people in online classes perform just as effectively as participants in conventional learning classes (Hew, Khe Foon; Jia, Chengyuan; Gonda, Donn Emmanuel; Bai, Shurui, December 21 2020). The use of online learning is becoming a pathway for learners with sparse access to physical courses so they can complete their degrees (Can refer futher to Veletsianos, George, 2020). Furthermore, digital classroom technologies allow those living remotely to access learning, and it enables the student to fit learning into their schedule more easily. There are many benefits of remote learning or flexible education can bring to those belong in the educational sector particularly to those belonging to the higher educational sector which will be discuss below.

2.0 FLEXIBILITY EFFECTS FOR ACADEMICIAN AND ADMINISTRATIVE STAFF OF THE UNIVERISTY

When we talk about educational sector which also include higher education institution, we tend to focus more on students. It is crucial to note that, the educational sector including the higher education institution also includes educators and administrative staff. Their present and huge contribution to the sector should not be denied by anyone. Similar like other employees working in any company or organizations, flexibility will bring many benefits to those working in the educational sector including in the higher education institution. Flexibility will allow them to manage their own hours and accomplish tasks in the comfort of their own home or from any desirable location. This at the end can increase work satisfaction, provide work life balance, and in some cases, help them to manage their lives more easily. Flexibility at work has been shown to boost organization morale and even increase productivity. As a result, more organizations are choosing to put flexible work arrangements in place in order to benefit both the employees and the organisation at large. When it's come to workers, flexibility or known as flexible working arrangements (FWA) might mean changes to hours of work (such as starting or finishing at different times), patterns of work (such as splitting shifts), or locations of work (such as working from home). Each of these arrangements has numerous benefits for both employees and employers (Leslie, L; Manchester, C; Park, T; Mehng, S, December 2012 and Kim, H; Gong, Y., 2017).

Among the benefits for employees includes flexible work might allow employees to work from home or from any preferable location, choose specific days to go into the office, extend or shorten their hours, take days off and arrange their own daily schedule. It will create healthy work life balance where most people feel satisfied when they can balance work requirements with spending time with family and friends. With a flexible timetable, employees can devote more hours to hobbies and social obligations while still completing their work tasks. Having a healthy work life balance means employees can manage their work hours in a way that

makes time for other things in their lives. It can also bring satisfaction to the job where those who manage their own schedule usually perform better during their working hours. Most employees demonstrate increased productivity, work performance and dedication to the organization when allowed to choose their own schedule. As a result, employees feel more satisfied with their job and might strive for higher positions within the organization. In the long-term, job satisfaction can lead to career development and personal growth. Working from home or from any desirable location can reduce sick days. Without travel obligations in place, employees are less likely to take a day off and can continue to work if they're able to maintain a satisfactory work performance. Those who work in the office can return home and finish the rest of their shift remotely. Sick employees are often encouraged by employer to spend a few extra days at home, and if they're able to continue working during that period it reduces their load when they return to the office. This can increase overall job satisfaction. Mental health is important for all professions and allows employees to enjoy their time at work. If people can work from home or from any preferable location and complete tasks around their own schedules, they may feel more supported by the organization. Flexible work arrangements can enable employees to take time to attend appointments during working hours and make up the time later. As a result, employees feel happier as their work hours support their daily needs. Employees might also feel encouraged to participate in educational courses or training sessions that can develop their professional skills. More free time during the week might help them learn new skills for the position that can increase their work performance. Opportunities for personal development may also allow employees to create long-term career goals. For example, someone who develops management skills might strive to become the next team leader. Beside employees, many benefits can also be gain by the management or the employers. Employers can also benefit from flexible work arrangements, whether it's from arranging their own weekly schedule or attracting talented employees who are pulled in by idea of a flexible work environment. Flexibility will allow employee retention. Most employers value employees that are dedicated to the organization and plan to stay with them for the foreseeable future. If people have the flexibility to manage their own schedules and experience increased productivity, they're likely to feel more excited about working for the organization. As a result, employee retention will increase. This can boost profitable income for a business and even encourage more customers to approach the organisation. With more employees working away from the office, organization may pay less for office supplies, food vendors, building space, meeting rooms and other resources. This can lower expenditure and boost overall profitability for a business. When employees have the opportunity to complete their work tasks away from the office, they may take less time off for sick days or appointments. Employers can save money on sick pay and other forms of paid leave if employees can continue to work from home or from any desirable location or make up hours spent at appointments during the day. This also helps maintain productivity levels with fewer loads passed on to other team members or interruptions to projects. The list of benefits over the idea of flexibility to workers is long to be discussed.

3.0 FLEXIBILITY EFFECTS FOR STUDENTS IN THE UNIVERSITY

Flexibility is a multifaceted concept. For students, this implies more convenient access to learning opportunities, greater choice of learning location, more control over their study schedules, and greater autonomy in managing their lives. (See Kaplan, Andreas M.; Haenlein, Michael, 2016 and Simonson, Michael and Berg, Gary A, 2023) On the other hand, for instructors, it enriches the course's pedagogy, produces new teaching resources, and introduces more varied and creative ways of assessing student assignments. There are many benefits for students if we allow flexibility to take place in the university. Students benefit from the flexibility of online education since it allows them to acquire better time-management skills and become more self-disciplined while gaining valuable life skills that they may apply in the profession. For instance, students who enrol in an online course are expected to complete assignments and exams just like those enrolled in a traditional classroom. Almost all work is submitted electronically, usually through certain platforms. Students are required to keep track of all requirements and deadlines and submit documents following the course schedule. Flexibility will also allow students to be more cost effective and save their pocket money. By allowing students to study from home or from any preferable location, there is no need for students to rent a room in the university campus or any house close to the university. Students would also be able to save their transportation and meals cost as there is no need for students to spend money to travel to the classroom in the campus or to buy foods and drinks. The money which they manage to save can later be used for other things which are more essential. Using flexibility or online education, student could also save their money from buying books or materials to do their assignment because everything can be done through online basis. This in the long term would able to reduce our long dependence on substances and materials which derived from nature. There is no need for us to produce papers anymore which can be wasteful and bring harm to nature and the environment.

Crucial for us to note that, the most significant difference between online education and the traditional

teaching method is the format and location of the classes. Traditional teaching methods of teaching require instructors to deliver knowledge to students in a face-to-face session on campus in the classroom or lecture hall. Online education is the opposite, as students do not need to go to a regular classroom or lecture hall to learn, they can learn with the help of a computer, tablet, or smartphone which they possess. Since online classes are delivered through the internet, online education is no longer limited by location and space, which creates a more relaxed and comfortable learning environment for the students and for the educators. Additionally, taking online classes helps avoid commuting. Instead of walking or driving to classroom or lecture hall every day and battling for a parking spot, online students simply walk to their computer or tablet and turn it on, saving time and effort. This could also reduce the level of tense and stress among students. By reducing their tense and stress, students can be more focus with their study in the university. The researcher humbly believes that every parent wants their children to perform well in the study. By implementing flexibility and online study in the university, their children can excel in their study. Important for us to remember numerous international students have been unable to return to their school sites since the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, owing to differences in entry and exit policies across countries or for a variety of other reasons. This is where the advantages of flexibility or online education come into play. Students are able to take courses from the comfort of their own homes in their own countries without disrupting their regular academic schedules, thanks to the flexibility of online learning.

In addition to the advantages of space, the schedule of online classes is also flexible and changeable. Rather than being required to participate in a physical or face-to-face class, students can choose where they want to learn and when they want to learn in most cases. The flexibility of online courses allows students to arrange their learning around their schedules and assures that they are in an optimal state to study and thus improving learning efficiency. Students in traditional physical or face-to-face classes occasionally encounter scheduling conflicts, but this is not a major issue in online classrooms. Students can plan their schedules without having to worry about their availability. Work schedules, as well as social and family obligations, can cause study time conflicts. Students enrolled in offline courses may find it challenging to fit everything into their schedules. Students taking offline courses may have difficulty fitting everything into their timetables. Online courses are the best way to solve this problem since students can include almost anything in their schedules and be an active student at the same time. We also could develop flexible learning approaches. Since different students have varied learning preferences, online courses with various modes and mediums have been expanded to meet all types of needs. Currently, many higher education institutions including in Malaysia offered students a variety of online course options, such as live ("synchronous"), recorded ("asynchronous"), and self-paced courses.

4.0 PATHWAY TO FLEXIBLE EDUCATION IN MALAYSIA

Though some efforts have been taken by the Malaysian government and universities in the past even before the Covid-19 pandemic to develop flexibility and online education, it is still not at the level which can be proud at. Only when Covid-19 struck in early 2020, then the government and the universities in the country started to fully embrace flexibility and online education. (Ida Lim, May, 30, 2020). At the beginning, many struggles adjusting themselves using any available technology in order to teach and learn. Both educators and students seem awkward to use technology as a new medium to teach and learn. This is because many already comfortable with the traditional way of teaching and learning namely by attending to classes and write notes on paper. However, after nearly two years being force/compel to use the technology, both educator and students finally able to adjust themselves to this new method of teaching and learning. To some extend they have to force/compel to become creative and expert in using technology to conduct online study. (Berita Harian, May 16, 2021). This show to us that, human being does have the abilities to improve themselves and to fit to the current new environment whenever the need arises. After few years using the technology, both the educators and students realize how many benefits they will able to get by adopting flexibility and technology for their own good. Having said so, Malaysian universities is still far away from fully adopting flexibility and online education. As the number of Covid-19 is put under control and the arrival of the national vaccination program, many universities in the country started to open their campus and "demand" educators, staffs, and students to come back to campus and resume face-to-face classes as if nothing had happened. Among the reason why the universities management demand the return to the face-to-face interaction is because they want to bring back life to the campus and avoid wastage of all the facilities which they have built for many years in the universities which is rather funny to the researcher. It is hard to change the existing mindset among local universities management. It will take many years before we can fully implement flexibility and remote education for the universities in the country. At the same time, it will require a lot of serious commitment from the government to put the initiative over flexibility and remote education into permanent reality.

Universities in Malaysia are generally categorised as public and private universities. Private universities include locally established universities and campuses of foreign universities. According to the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE), up to September 2023, Malaysia has 20 public universities, 404 private universities, 36 polytechnic and 105 community colleges. (MOHE official website, 2023). Interestingly, among all the universities in the country, there is one particular university in the country which really focus on the idea of flexibility and online education. The Open University Malaysia, abbreviated as OUM, is the 7th private university in Malaysia. It is owned by Multimedia Technology Enhancement Operations (METEOR) Sdn. Bhd, a consortium of 11 Malaysian public universities. The main campus is located at Menara OUM, Kelana Centre Point, Kelana Jaya, Selangor. In addition to this, there are more than 30 learning centres throughout Malaysia, out of which 10 are regional learning centres. As the first open and distance learning university in the country, OUM initially opened to 753 learners in 2001. A decade later, OUM has over 100,000 students in more than 50 academic programmes. In 2023, QS Stars had assessed OUM's online learning for three years and granted OUM a 5-Star rating. This university can become a good role model and source of reference for other universities in the country to follow if they really want to implement flexibility and online education effectively. (OUM official website, 2023).

5.0 FLEXIBILITY AND REMOTE EDUCATION IS THE KEY IF WE WANT STUDENTS TO CONNECT WITH THEIR STUDIES

Flexibility and remote or online education could bring many benefits to everyone belonging to the educational sector particularly to the higher education. By connecting students with flexible, high-quality study and professional development opportunities, we can assist them in broadening their perspectives and developing new abilities that will enable them to thrive in a global economy and challenge. The Covid-19 pandemic has been responsible for a great many things, including the exposure of something endemic in higher education: learner variability. This is not new. Institutions of higher education have long ignored or paid lip service to the fact that students come from multiple ethnic and cultural backgrounds, that they have differing needs, abilities, disabilities and constraints. Now we've had it laid bare, perhaps more than ever before, those students are studying while holding down (often precarious) jobs, caring for family members and dealing with their own physical and mental health issues. The shift to online education was in fact a great windfall for many students, who found the flexibility it brought to be life-changing. Education, suddenly, became much more accessible. And, to top it off, universities had to take notice because it hurt their bottom line if they weren't accessible and accommodating to this new reality. By offering flexibility in the times and ways students could take classes, universities could maintain or even increase enrolments. The time has come for everyone to realize that, time has change, we cannot keep forcing everyone including universities student to go back to the era before Covid-19 pandemic started. Some people tend to use the word bring back normality to justify their argument in order to force people including students to go back to the old way of study. Normal here should not be limited to physical or face-to face study only; it should be broadened to include new way of study through flexibility and remote or online education. The country policy makers and government need to developed a comprehensive national policy plan on flexibility and remote or online education so that everyone can fully understand about this matter and take the necessary and serious steps to make the necessary changes. In order to bring success, the government need to allocate certain amount of money from the country yearly budget announcement for this matter. Educators and administrative staffs in the university need to be properly trained so that they have enough skills to adopt this new method of teaching and learning. Universities in the country need to improve their existing facilities and fill it with facilities which are more up to date and fulfil the demand to make flexibility and remote or online education effective.

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REFERENCE LIST

- COVIDNOW in Malaysia. (2022). The official Malaysia government website for data and insights on COVID-19. <https://covidnow.moh.gov.my/>. Retrieved on December 15, 2022.
- Deflem, Mathieu (2021). "The Right to Teach in a Hyper-Digital Age: Legal Protections for (Post-) Pandemic Concerns". *Society*. 58 (3): 204–212. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8161721/>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- Dextor Tilo. (2023). Malaysia's employment act changes now in effect. <https://www.hcamag.com/asia/specialisation/employment-law/malaysias-employment-act-changes-now-in-effect/431693>. Retrieved on September 22, 2023.
- Employment Act amendment covers all workers regardless of salary – MOHR. (2022). Malaysiakini. <https://www.malaysiakini.com/news/615627>. Retrieved on May 19, 2023.
- Enforcement of Employment Act amendment postponed to Jan 1. (2022). Free Malaysia Today. <https://www.freemalaysiatoday.com/category/nation/2022/08/26/enforcement-of-employment-act-amendment-postponed-to-jan-1/>. Retrieved on May 19, 2023.
- Guru perlu lebih kreatif mengajar ketika pandemik. (2021). <https://www.bharian.com.my/berita/nasional/2021/05/817228/guru-perlu-lebih-kreatif-mengajar-ketika-pandemik>. Retrieved on September 21, 2023.
- Hew, Khe Foon; Jia, Chengyuan; Gonda, Donn Emmanuel; Bai, Shurui (21 December 2020). "Transitioning to the "new normal" of learning in unpredictable times: pedagogical practices and learning performance in fully online flipped classrooms". *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*. 17 (1): 57. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7750097/>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- HR Ministry: Employees can apply for flexible work arrangements when Employment Act amendment comes into force on Sept 1. (2022). Malay Mail. <https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2022/06/23/hr-ministry-employees-can-apply-for-flexible-work-arrangements-when-employment-act-amendment-comes-into-force-on-sept-1/13935>. Retrieved on May 19, 2023.
- Ida Lim. (2020). Reality for Malaysia's university students: Online learning challenges, stress, workload; possible solutions for fully digital future until Dec. Malay Mail <https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2020/05/30/reality-for-malaysias-university-students-online-learning-challenges-stress/1870717>. Retrieved on September 21, 2023.
- Jonathan Raymond. (2020). Georgia awards \$21 million in digital learning grants | Here's what Atlanta area districts got. <https://www.11alive.com/article/news/health/coronavirus/georgia-school-districts-digital-learning-grants-atlanta/85-3a783e3c-2642-44e9-8fa6-090012604481>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- Junhairi Alyasa. (2020). Covid-19: Perintah Kawalan Pergerakan di seluruh negara bermula 18 Mac. Sinar Harian. <https://www.sinarharian.com.my/article/74100/KHAS/Covid-19/Covid-19-Perintah-Kawalan-Pergerakan-di-seluruh-negara-bermula-18-Mac>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- Kaplan, Andreas M.; Haenlein, Michael. (2016). "Higher education and the digital revolution: About MOOCs, SPOCs, social media, and the Cookie Monster". *Business Horizons*. 59 (4): 441–50. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S000768131630009X?via%3Dihub> Retrieved on September 21, 2023.
- Kim, H; Gong, Y (2017). "Effects of work-family and family-work conflicts on flexible work arrangements demand: A gender role perspective". *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*. 28 (20): 2936–2956. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09585192.2016.1164217>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- Leslie, L; Manchester, C; Park, T; Mehng, S (December 2012). "Flexible Work Practices: A Source of Career Premiums or Penalties?". *The Academy of Management Journal*. 55 (6): 1407–1428. <https://journals.aom.org/doi/10.5465/amj.2010.0651>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- MOHE official website. (2023). Number of Institution of Higher Learning. <https://www.mohe.gov.my/>. Retrieved on September 21, 2023.

- Mukhtar, Khadijah; Javed, Kainat; Arooj, Mahwish; Sethi, Ahsan (May 2020). "Advantages, Limitations and Recommendations for online learning during COVID-19 pandemic era". *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*. 36 (COVID19–S4): S27–S31. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7306967/>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- Ng, Kate. (2020). "Coronavirus: Malaysia cases rise by 190 after mosque event as imams urge online services". *The Independent*. Archived from the original on 5 April 2020. <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/asia/coronavirus-malaysia-cases-southeast-asia-mosque-islam-a9403816.html>. Retrieved on August 24, 2022.
- OUM official website. (2023). Open University Malaysia (OUM). <https://www.oum.edu.my/>. Retrieved on September 21, 2023.
- Shathana Kasinathan. (2023). Ministry introduces hybrid, flexible learning system: mandatory university attendance only in first, final years. *Malay Mail*. <https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2023/06/04/ministry-introduces-hybrid-flexible-learning-system-mandatory-university-attendance-only-in-first-final-years/72449>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- Simonson, Michael and Berg, Gary A. "Distance learning". *Encyclopedia Britannica*. 17 February 2023. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/distance-learning>. Retrieved on September 21, 2023.
- Sipalan, Joseph; Holmes, Sam. (2020). "Malaysia confirms first cases of coronavirus infection". *Reuters*. Archived from the original on 18 February 2020. <https://www.reuters.com/article/china-health-malaysia/malaysia-confirms-first-cases-of-coronavirus-infection-idUSL4N29U03A>. Retrieved on August 24, 2022.
- Southeast Asia Covid-19 Tracker. (2020). Center for Strategic and International Studies. <https://www.csis.org/programs/southeast-asia-program/projects/past-projects/southeast-asia-covid-19-tracker>. Retrieved on December 15, 2022.
- The Prime Minister's Special Message on COVID-19 - 16 March 2020. Prime Minister's Office of Malaysia. Archived from the original on 11 August 2021. <https://web.archive.org/web/20210811085344/https://www.pmo.gov.my/2020/03/perutusan-khas-yab-perdana-menteri-mengenai-covid-19-16-mac-2020/>. Retrieved on August 24, 2022.
- UNESCO. (2020). 290 million students out of school due to COVID-19: UNESCO releases first global numbers and mobilizes response. <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/290-million-students-out-school-due-covid-19-unesco-releases-first-global-numbers-and-mobilizes>. Retrieved on September 20, 2023.
- Veletsianos, George (2020). *Learning online: The student experience*. Johns Hopkins University. Press. Baltimore, Maryland.